

Effect of Substrate Temperature on the Properties of CuZnS Thin Films Prepared by Vacuum Spray Pyrolysis

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Abstract

Copper Zinc Sulphide (CZS) thin films have been deposited on a glass substrate at different temperatures using Chemical Spray Pyrolysis technique under a vacuum of 10^{-3} Torr. The influence of substrate temperature on the structural, morphological, optical and electrical characteristics of CZS thin films are investigated and reported. The major advantage of this material is that it uses earth-abundant and low-cost constituent elements like Copper, Zinc, and Sulphur. The band gap of the as-deposited films are obtained in the range of 2.36 to 3.2 eV, which makes it a good absorber as well as window layer. The band gap was found to increase with increasing Zn concentration. Structural analysis shows highly crystalline nature with a mixed phase of CuS-ZnS. SEM image shows the homogeneous distribution of closely packed grains without any gap in between. EDX data clearly shows the peaks corresponding to Cu, Zn, and S. The optical properties of the films were studied using UV-Vis-NIR spectrometer. A peak shift has been observed on increasing the substrate temperature of the films. The electrical properties have been investigated using Hall measurement system and all the samples are found to have P-type conductivity.

Keywords: Copper Zinc Sulphide; Vacuum Spray Pyrolysis; p-type semiconductor